

КУЛЬТУРНІ ПРАКТИКИ

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antonivska_maryna@ukr.net***FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDING AS A FACTOR OF INTERCULTURAL
COMMUNICATION ACHIEVEMENT AND INDICATOR OF VALUABLE
SELF-DETERMINATION OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL
ESTABLISHMENTS STUDENTS**

The purpose of the work is to clarify the role and influence of the foreign language on the process of intercultural communication as the main component of students' self-determination in modern higher educational system of Ukraine; to determine by which factors the process of intercultural communication becomes more effective in interacting with representatives of different cultures. **The research methodology** consisted in the application of such research methods as study, analysis and generalization with the purpose of revealing the concept of intercultural communication as a factor in the formation of interethnic consent in all spheres of communication. **Scientific novelty** of the work lies in the description of the problem of mastering intercultural interaction. In this regard, the research proves that in our time as never before, foreign language and the process of its knowledge affect preferences in choosing vital important values. It helps students to dive into social, economic, political and cultural trends of modern globalized world. Modern student should be capable of recognizing valuable orientations.

The problems of communication, value orientations formation, formation of linguistic culture elements have been extensively covered in the scientific literature, but despite this, the problem of intercultural communication as the main indicator of person's value formation in the process of international activity remains insufficiently studied. Particular emphasis is placed on the fact that learning foreign language, at least one, allows not only deeper realize national identity of other countries and become familiar with theirs culture, habits, customs, but with a sufficiently high level of cultural competence provides an opportunity to participate in the dialogue of cultures. In these processes, a special role is played by intercultural communication that can not only become a means enhancing the overall competence of the individual, but also can significantly impact on the processes of its self-determination. **Conclusions.** It is proved that from self-determination in culture and through the help of cultures depend the relationship of the individual with other people, attitudes to own activities, awareness of own individuality therefore, the study of a foreign language determines not only the use of certain acquired skills and skills of communication, but also gives peculiarities of the host country's linguistic picture of the world, linguistic and extra-linguistic factors that

determine communication. As a result of such activity new forms of cultural space are born, which hardly affect other people, but they play a key role in the process of interaction.

Key words: intercultural communication; communication; foreign language; culture; cultural competence; foreign conceptual sphere.

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Вивчення іноземної мови як чинника досягнення інтеркультурної комунікації та індикатора ціннісного самовизначення студентів ЗВО

Мета роботи – з'ясувати роль та вплив іноземної мови на процес інтеркультурної комунікації як основної складової самовизначення студентів у сучасній системі вищої освіти України. Визначити завдяки яким факторам процес інтеркультурної комунікації стає більш ефективним у взаємодії з представниками різних культур. **Методологія дослідження** базується на використанні таких методів дослідження як вивчення, аналіз та узагальнення з метою розкриття поняття інтеркультурної комунікації як чинника до формування міжнаціональної згоди у всіх сферах спілкування. **Наукова новизна** роботи полягає в описі проблеми опанування інтеркультурної взаємодії. У зв'язку з цим дослідження доводить, що в наш час іноземна мова та процес її пізнання впливає на переваги при виборі життєво важливих цінностей. Це допомагає студентам орієнтуватися та дотримуватися соціальних, економічних, політичних та культурних тенденцій сучасного світу. Модерновий студент має бути здатним розставляти та правильно детермінувати ціннісні пріоритети та орієнтири. У науковій літературі досить широко диференціюються проблеми комунікації, формування ціннісних орієнтирів, формування елементів мовної культури, але незважаючи на це, недостатньо вивченою залишається проблема інтеркультурної комунікації як основного показника ціннісного формування особистості в процесі міжнародної діяльності.

Саме тому, вивчення іноземної мови, принаймні однієї, дозволяє не тільки глибше усвідомити національну ідентичність інших країн та ознайомитися з їх культурою, звичаями, звичками, але з досить високим рівнем культурної компетенції дає можливість брати участь у діалозі культур. У цих процесах особливу роль відіграє інтеркультурна комунікація, яка може не тільки стати засобом підвищення загальної компетенції особистості, але також суттєво впливати на процеси її самовизначення. **Висновки.** Доведено, що від самовизначення в культурі та за допомогою культур залежать відносини особи з іншими людьми, ставлення до власної діяльності, усвідомлення власної індивідуальності, тому саме вивчення іноземної мови обумовлює не лише використання певних набутих вмінь та навичок комунікації, але надає обізнаності щодо особливостей мовної картини світу країни перебування, лінгвістичних і екстралінгвістичних чинників, що обумовлюють комунікацію. У результаті такої діяльності народжуються нові форми культурного простору, які практично не впливають на інших людей, проте відіграють ключову роль у процесі інтеракції.

Ключові слова: інтеркультурна комунікація; комунікація; іноземна мова; культура; культурна компетенція; іншомовна концептосфера.

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Изучение иностранного языка как фактора достижения интеркультурной коммуникации и индикатора ценностного самоопределения студентов высших учебных заведений

Цель работы – выяснить роль и влияние иностранного языка на процесс интеркультурной коммуникации как основной составляющей самоопределения студентов в современной системе высшего образования Украины. Определить благодаря каким факторам процесс интеркультурной коммуникации становится более эффективным во взаимодействии с представителями разных культур. **Методология исследования** базируется на использовании таких методов исследования как изучение, анализ и обобщение с целью раскрытия понятия интеркультурной коммуникации как фактора к формированию межнационального согласия во всех сферах общения. **Научная новизна** заключается в описании проблемы освоения интеркультурного взаимодействия. В связи с этим, исследование доказывает, что в наше время как никогда, иностранный язык и процесс его познания влияет на предпочтения при выборе жизненно важных ценностей. Это помогает студентам ориентироваться и соблюдать социальные, экономические, политические и культурные тенденции современного мира. Модерновый студент должен быть способен расставлять и правильно детерминировать ценностные приоритеты и ориентиры. В научной литературе достаточно широко дифференцируются проблемы коммуникации, формирования ценностных ориентиров, формирование элементов языковой культуры, но несмотря на это, недостаточно изученной остается проблема интеркультурной коммуникации как основного показателя ценностного формирования личности в процессе международной деятельности.

Именно поэтому, изучение иностранного языка, по крайней мере одного, позволяет не только глубже осознать национальную идентичность других стран и ознакомиться с их культурой, обычаями, привычками, но с достаточно высоким уровнем культурной компетенции, дает возможность участвовать в диалоге культур. В этих процессах особую роль играет интеркультурная коммуникация, которая может не только стать средством повышения общей компетенции личности, но также существенно влиять на процессы ее самоопределения. **Выводы.** Доказано, что от самоопределения в культуре и с помощью культур зависят отношения лица с другими людьми, отношение к собственной деятельности, осознание собственной индивидуальности, поэтому именно изучение иностранного языка обуславливает не только использование определенных приобретенных умений и навыков коммуникации, но предоставляет осведомленности об особенностях языковой картины мира страны пребывания, лингвистических и экстралингвистических факторов, обуславливающих коммуникацию. В результате такой деятельности рождаются новые формы

культурного пространства, которые практически не влияют на других людей, однако играют ключевую роль в процессе интеракции.

Ключевые слова: интеркультурная коммуникация; коммуникация; иностранный язык; культура; культурная компетенция; иноязычная концептосферы.

Introduction. It is known that higher education and science are becoming a global factor in social development and are among the most important national and global priorities. The internationalization of living space presupposes a certain universal system in education, but it is possible only if the diversity of social, political, cultural and linguistic traditions of different countries in a rapidly changing and increasingly interdependent world is preserved. A significant obstacle to the intensive development of internationalization is the low level of proficiency in foreign languages. Meanwhile, knowledge of a foreign language is a guarantee of social security in modern society.

Nowadays foreign language in Ukrainian education becomes an important condition for the integration of younger generation into the modern society and influences preferences in choosing vital important values.

It helps students to dive into social, economic, political and cultural trends of modern globalized world. Learning foreign language, at least one, allows not only deeper realize national identity of other countries and become familiar with their culture, habits, customs but with a sufficiently high level of cultural competence provides an opportunity to participate in the dialogue of cultures. In these processes, a special role is played by intercultural communication that can not only become a means enhancing the overall competence of the individual, but also significantly affect on the processes of its self-determination. From self-determination in culture and through the help of cultures depend the relationship of the individual with other people, attitudes to own activities, awareness of own individuality. As a result of such activity new forms of cultural space are born, which hardly affect other people.

The essence of culture is such that in the process of itself contact with the culture occurs “feeding” of moral, spiritual, creative human resources, bringing individual to rethink positions, reevaluating established beliefs. As a result, of these contacts we widely develop and enrich our spiritual and moral outlook.

Intercultural communication can influence personal development processes, including self-determination processes. In the process of successful intercultural communication occurs the introduction of the individual to the culture, the assimilation of existing habits, norms of behavior, etc.

In the case of successful learning process, we may admit that students have the raise of intrinsic motivation in foreign language learning, understanding and the adoption of the culture of the studied language, and ultimately, increases the dynamics of students’ value orientations. Every lesson teacher should try to do the process of learning language more effective, using different methods of verbal and intellectual activity.

Actual scientific researches and issues analysis. Concerning the theory of the issue of intercultural communication, the analysis of special literature shows that this issue is under active discussion. The main points of the discussion relate to the interpretation of the concept itself, components of this type of communication, as well as

the search for optimal ways of forming intercultural communication as the main component of person's self-determination. The problem of the interconnected mastery of language and culture has always been an interest both for foreign and domestic linguists and scientists.

Theoretical and methodological basis of the study was composed of modern sociological, cultural, psychological and pedagogical ideas and concepts of foreign language teaching, interaction between the individual and the social environment, education, the leading role of activity in the process of personal development. Our understanding of the term "intercultural communication" was made by R. Lado works in the field of the theory of intercultural communication. General theoretical approaches to the process of education as the adherence of the younger generation to the cultural values of humanity, embodied in the works of S. I. Gessen, E. Passov. Our understanding of intercultural communication as a free, value-regulatory process was created by works of such famous scientists and researches as G. Almond, Z. Bauman, A. R. Biruni, E. McGrew, J. Meyer, F. Heider, J. Passeron, J. Page.

Modern scientists in a way of an active discussion are looking for means to organize interdependent language and culture education both in the field of learning foreign languages, and in others. Thus, G. Gryshenkova examines the problem of language and socio-cultural training of management personnel through the organization of business games.

Such modern researchers of intercultural communication concept as E. Vereshchagin, V. Kostomarov, E. Pasov, V. Safonov, S. Ter-Minasova develop theoretical substantiation and offer practical recommendations on how to teach students foreign language within the limits of a competent approach, mastering socio-cultural information and for its application in accordance with world standards of communication (Vereshchagin and Kostomarov 1990). In the works of scientists, great attention is devoted to solving the issues of students studying, the peculiarities of intercultural communication in a foreign language, such as rules and norms of behavior in a foreign language environment, value orientations of representatives of another culture, the interpretation of cultural information.

Selection of previously unsolved parts of the whole problem.

In modern Ukrainian educational sphere, students' self-determination is one of the main pedagogical and educational goals, and the core of the teachers work in this case is providing of general pedagogical assistance to the student, which is one of the most important issues for his personal development. Moreover, education is not imposes certain values, instead, it creates conditions for recognition, understanding and choosing the values of culture: stimulates this choice and subsequent internal work of the individual on their valuable priorities (Donec, 2001, p. 19).

In the modern educational practice of not only Ukrainian higher educational establishments, there is a need to resolve the contradiction between the requirement presented by society to the modern university in graduate preparation as an individual possessing not only high level of awareness and development of specialized professional skills, but also having a high level of different spiritual and moral characteristics. Modern student should be capable of recognizing valuable orientations (Dzhurinskij,

2000, p. 96). And in this case, foreign language is the main point in process of achieving cultural oriented basis.

Therefore, **the purpose** of this article is to highlight theoretical foundations of the influence of intercultural communication on the activation of the processes of students' value self-determination and the development of appropriate effective pedagogical practice in higher education field.

Achieving this goal involves solving the following **tasks**:

- to study existing approaches to understanding the phenomenon of «intercultural communication» and its impact on the students' self-determination;
- to reveal pedagogical essence and specificity of the intercultural communication influence on the processes of students' self-determination;
- to determine the criteria for the successful influence of intercultural communication on the students' self-determination, identify patterns and principles that influence the increase in the effectiveness of this influence.

The object of the research is the processes of students' value self-determination.

The subject of the study is foreign language studying as a factor of intercultural achievement and indicator of valuable self-determination.

The statement of basic materials. *Intercultural communication is a process of communication and interaction, which occurs between representatives of different cultures or cultural communities* (Glepson, 2000, p. 277). Intercultural communication is a source of personal transformations in a human, because it contains possibilities for presenting to an individual a wide range of value-regulating principles for self-construction and self-improvement. Meeting with culture in the process of intercultural communication is the establishment of a spiritual connection between oneself and a foreign-speaking world and people, experiencing a sense of belonging to a national culture, interiorizing its values and, as a result, building one's own life with their manner. The result of personality enculturation is value self-determination based on the reflexive understanding of one's positions, the system of relations, preferences, and value orientations. These processes will be most active if:

- the educational process will be built on a dialogical basis;
- the educational process will be increased by cultural competence of students;
- the process of communication practice in the classes of a foreign language will take place with a focus on the value priorities of the studied language culture.

In the case of successful learning process, we may admit that students have the raise of intrinsic motivation in foreign language learning, understanding and the adoption of the culture of the studied language, and ultimately, increases the dynamics of students' value orientations.

We are inclined to the opinion of the researcher N. Kostenko, who believes that “foreign-language professional competence is defined as the ability to apply:

- knowledge of lexical-grammatical features of a foreign language, types of foreign language discourses, their structure;
- the ability and skills to perceive, interpret, ensure the coherence of expressions in meaningful communicative models and to create discourse in typical professional situations. In addition to linguistic knowledge, skills and abilities, foreign language

professional competence is formed on the basis of the components of professional competence and foreign language communicative competence” (2012, pp. 16–17).

Nowadays, we are considering professional competence of students in universities as a component of foreign communication competence, and believe that it is formed by students’ familiarizing with professional texts, communicating with native speakers, familiarizing with the latest scientific achievements in one or another field of science of the country whose language is studied, the expansion of general erudition, which is extremely important for a future specialist. Thus, the result of the formation of a foreign language competence is the linguistic personality, which is a universal, general pedagogical category, characterized by such qualities of personality as emancipation, creativity, independence, ability to build rapport and interaction with communication partners (Passov, 1991, p. 87).

Also, it should be noted that the formation of linguistic and sociocultural competence implies preserving of sociocultural identity of communicants. That’s why, one of the most valuable experience for students is internship in a country which language is being studied and further work in conditions of communication with different societies representatives.

But formation of linguistic and cultural competence using a variety of informational sources in class conditions is also very important. So, in this case the role of pedagogical activity in formation of intercultural communication is that the teacher directs communicative activities according to ethnic and cultural peculiarities of communication subjects, broadcasts and in a certain way decodes cultural-historical and ethnonational codes, inherent to one or another ethnic communities.

Every lesson teacher should try to do the process of learning language more effective, using different methods of verbal and intellectual activity. Thus, one of the most important forms of educational process organization is practical-oriented manner of teaching students, as teachers in their work are focused on the preparation of new generation specialists, deeply aware of international theory, possessing skills of analysis, modeling, forecasting of international relations, planning foreign policy that master information technologies and art of intercultural communication.

Based on this, we may state that usage of videos, films, serials and phonograms for information presentation that has important meaning in linguistic and socio-cultural terms, is a condition to facilitate the perception of historical, socio- and ethnocultural background, understanding and perception socio-cultural-driven scenarios and national-specific behavior patterns, relief analysis and comparison with similar ones phenomena in native culture, fixing of norms and standards of linguistic and non-verbal behavior in standardize situations of communication

Newspapers and magazines articles represent a national culture, because they contain information about political, economic, socio-cultural processes of modern society and reflect the specifics of world outlook, world perception of native speakers – representatives of another culture; and secondly, these materials are a model of national-cultural; thirdly, reading of genuine foreign-language publicistic texts has a real motivation, because in the absence of foreign-language and cultural environment the most realistic kind of communication is mediated intercultural communication.

Besides, selection of texts for reading should be carried out with the purpose of actualization of the processes of value comprehension of the studied culture, spiritual and moral self-reinforcement, promoting the development of ideas and concepts of value life reference points. (Wiseman, 2003, p. 374)

It is also obvious that usage of situational role-playing with particular theatrical elements, brain storms, round table methods, lively discussions, emotional, reflexive polylogs, monologs and dialogs, quizzes, language guesses highly motivate students to dive deeply into foreign language, try to better understand cultural differences, language peculiarities.

In addition, to increase the cultural competence of students we have a method of business game it is one of the leading methods of active learning. In the process of constructing a business game are selected situations that most reflect the intercultural aspect in communication. The use of all these forms and methods allows you to engage any of the values in the self-determination process

Conclusions and suggestions. Throughout all life, a person lives in the world of culture, through which he is formed, acquires the opportunity to understand the principles of the world structure around him and his place in this world. However, not always and not every culture is assimilated by man independently. To explain and introduce its manifestations at the ethnic, national, and civilizational levels, extensive work of teachers is needed. If a person perceives the native culture from childhood, plunging into it immediately after birth, and the school and the teacher are only part of the upbringing process, then in foreign culture studying a foreign language teacher becomes a guide in the world of information, and in some cases almost its only source.

In the process of successful intercultural communication, in-culture process takes place – the individual is introduced to culture, assimilates existing habits, norms, and behavioral patterns characteristic of a given culture. In the process of intensive practice in a foreign language, the individual comprehends the value orientations of the culture of the language being studied. His own value orientations may undergo significant dynamics due to the emerging contradiction between various opposing meanings, when a person has an opposition to values or disagreement in the structures of the old and new experience of activity. The result of personality enculturation (appropriation by the individual of values, knowledge, ideals of a given cultural environment) is value-cultural self-determination and the identification of one's own positions, attitudes, preferences, value bases in the interaction with the same cultural components.

The effectiveness of the process of influence of intercultural communication on students value self-determination depends on the interaction of various factors, conditions and prerequisites. The main factors proved in our study were: the humanistic nature of the interaction between students and teacher in the classroom; personal meaning of learning, usage of innovative methods and techniques in the learning process. The success of these factors is ensured by building a learning process on a dialogical basis; increasing the cultural competence of students; the implementation of the practice of communication in the classroom with a focus on the value priorities of the culture of the target language.

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